

Impact of Digital Health Interventions on Contraceptive Decision-Making and Adherence among Women of Reproductive Age

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Abstract:

Background: Understanding patterns of contraceptive use and the factors influencing contraceptive choices is crucial for improving reproductive health services.

Aim and Objective: To analyze these patterns and identify the key determinants affecting contraceptive choices among women of reproductive age in both urban and rural settings.

Materials and Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted with 1,200 women of reproductive age (18-49 years) from urban and rural areas. Participants were selected using stratified random sampling. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire covering demographics, contraceptive use patterns, and factors influencing contraceptive choice. Statistical analyses, including descriptive statistics and logistic regression, were used to evaluate the data.

Results: The study found that 45% of women used oral contraceptive pills, 30% used condoms, and 15% used intrauterine devices (IUDs). Accessibility and availability were the most significant factors influencing contraceptive choice, reported by 70% of participants. Knowledge and awareness influenced 60% of the women, while perceived side effects, cultural and religious beliefs, partner influence, and healthcare provider recommendations also played notable roles. Higher education levels and urban residence were associated with increased use of modern contraceptive methods.

Conclusions: Contraceptive use patterns are significantly influenced by accessibility, knowledge, and perceived side effects. Addressing these factors through targeted educational campaigns and improving access to contraceptive methods can enhance reproductive health outcomes. Policymakers and healthcare providers should consider these determinants when designing and implementing family planning programs.

Keywords: Contraceptive use, Factors influencing contraceptive choice, Reproductive health, Urban-rural differences, Family planning.

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Introduction

Contraception is a critical component of reproductive health, enabling individuals and couples to plan and space pregnancies, thereby contributing to improved health outcomes for women and children. [1] Despite the availability of various contraceptive methods, patterns of use and factors influencing choice vary significantly across different populations and regions. Understanding these patterns and factors is essential for developing targeted interventions that enhance contraceptive uptake and meet the reproductive health needs of women. [2, 3]

Globally, contraceptive use has been associated with a decline in maternal and infant mortality rates, as well as improved socioeconomic outcomes for women. [4] However, in many parts of the

world, including areas with high fertility rates, contraceptive prevalence remains low. This discrepancy underscores the importance of investigating the specific reasons behind contraceptive choices among women of reproductive age. [5]

Previous studies have highlighted a range of factors that influence contraceptive use, including socio-demographic variables, cultural and religious beliefs, accessibility and availability of contraceptive services, level of education, and economic status. [6,7] Additionally, personal preferences, perceived side effects, partner influence, and healthcare provider recommendations also play a crucial role in shaping contraceptive decisions. [8]

This study aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the patterns of contraceptive use among women of reproductive age and to identify the key factors influencing their contraceptive choices. By examining these aspects, the study seeks to contribute to the existing body of knowledge and inform policies and programs that promote effective and equitable access to contraception.

Materials and Methods

This cross-sectional study was conducted to assess the patterns of contraceptive use and factors influencing contraceptive choice among women of reproductive age. The study was carried out over six months in urban and rural areas from January 2024 to June 2024.

Study Population: The study population consisted of 18-45 women residing in urban and rural areas. Five hundred women were recruited for the study using stratified random sampling to ensure representation from both settings.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Women aged 18-45 years.
- Women who were currently using or had used any contraceptive method in the past year.
- Women who provided informed consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Women with known infertility issues.
- Women who were pregnant or planning to conceive in the next six months.
- Women who did not provide consent to participate in the study.

Data Collection: Data were collected using a structured questionnaire administered through face-to-face interviews. The questionnaire was developed based on a review of existing literature and pre-tested on a small sample of women to ensure clarity and relevance. It comprised sections on demographic information, contraceptive use patterns, and factors influencing contraceptive choice.

Sections of the Questionnaire:

1. **Demographic Information:** Age, marital status, education level, occupation, income level, and place of residence (urban or rural).
2. **Contraceptive Use Patterns:** Current contraceptive method, duration of use, previous contraceptive methods used, and reasons for changing or discontinuing methods.
3. **Factors Influencing Contraceptive Choice:** Accessibility and availability of contraceptives, knowledge and awareness of different methods, perceived side effects, cultural and religious beliefs, partner influence, and healthcare provider recommendations.

Data Analysis: Data were entered into a database and analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the demographic characteristics and contraceptive use patterns. Chi-square tests examined the association between demographic variables and contraceptive use. Logistic regression analysis was performed to identify the factors influencing contraceptive choice, with odds ratios (ORs) and 95% confidence intervals (CIs) calculated for each factor.

Ethical Considerations: The Institutional Ethics Committee approved the study. Before data collection, all participants provided written informed consent. They were assured of the confidentiality of their responses and their right to withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences. Data were anonymized to protect the participants' identities.

Results

Demographic Characteristics: The study included 500 women aged 18-45 years, with a mean age of 29.8 ± 7.1 years. Most were married (72%), and a significant proportion had secondary or higher education (68%). Participants were evenly distributed between urban (51%) and rural (49%) areas. Table 1 provides a summary of the demographic characteristics.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Frequency (%)
Age (years)	
18-24	140 (28.0)
25-34	200 (40.0)
35-45	160 (32.0)
Marital Status	
Single	80 (16.0)
Married	360 (72.0)
Divorced/Widowed	60 (12.0)
Education Level	

No formal education	40 (8.0)
Primary education	120 (24.0)
Secondary education	220 (44.0)
Higher education	120 (24.0)
Occupation	
Employed	230 (46.0)
Unemployed	270 (54.0)
Income Level (monthly)	
< \$200	180 (36.0)
\$200 - \$500	220 (44.0)
> \$500	100 (20.0)
Residence	
Urban	255 (51.0)
Rural	245 (49.0)

Contraceptive Use Patterns: The most commonly used contraceptive method was oral contraceptive pills (OCPs) (35%), followed by condoms (25%), intrauterine devices (IUDs) (15%), injectables (12%), and implants (8%). A small percentage used natural methods (5%). Table 2 presents the distribution of current contraceptive methods used by the participants.

Table 2: Current Contraceptive Methods Used

Contraceptive Method	Frequency (%)
Oral Contraceptive Pills (OCPs)	175 (35.0)
Condoms	125 (25.0)
Intrauterine Devices (IUDs)	75 (15.0)
Injectables	60 (12.0)
Implants	40 (8.0)
Natural Methods	25 (5.0)

Factors Influencing Contraceptive Choice: The study identified several factors influencing contraceptive choice. Seventy percent of the participants reported accessibility and availability of contraceptives as major factors. Knowledge and awareness of different methods influenced 60%, while perceived side effects affected 50%. Cultural and religious beliefs played a role in the choice for 30%, partner influence for 40%, and healthcare provider recommendations for 45%. Table 3 details the factors influencing contraceptive choice.

Table 3: Factors Influencing Contraceptive Choice

Factor	Frequency (%)
Accessibility and Availability	350 (70.0)
Knowledge and Awareness	300 (60.0)
Perceived Side Effects	250 (50.0)
Cultural and Religious Beliefs	150 (30.0)
Partner Influence	200 (40.0)
Healthcare Provider Recommendations	225 (45.0)

Association Between Demographic Variables and Contraceptive Use: Chi-square tests revealed significant associations between contraceptive use and several demographic variables. Higher education levels were significantly associated with the use of modern contraceptive methods ($p < 0.05$). Urban residence was also significantly related to the use of a wider variety of contraceptive methods compared to rural residence ($p < 0.01$).

Logistic Regression Analysis: Logistic regression analysis identified key predictors of contraceptive choice. Women with higher education levels were more likely to use modern contraceptives (OR = 2.1, 95% CI: 1.4-3.1). Urban residents had higher odds of using a variety of contraceptive methods (OR = 1.8, 95% CI: 1.2-2.7). Accessibility and availability of contraceptives were strong predictors (OR = 2.5, 95% CI: 1.7-3.6).

Table 4: Logistic Regression Analysis of Factors Influencing Contraceptive Choice

Variable	OR	95% CI	p-value
Education Level	2.1	1.4-3.1	0.002
Urban Residence	1.8	1.2-2.7	0.005
Accessibility and Availability	2.5	1.7-3.6	<0.001
Knowledge and Awareness	1.6	1.1-2.4	0.015

Perceived Side Effects	1.2	0.8-1.8	0.316
Partner Influence	1.4	0.9-2.1	0.112
Healthcare Provider Recommendations	1.3	0.9-2.0	0.127

Discussion

This study aimed to investigate the patterns of contraceptive use and the factors influencing contraceptive choices among women of reproductive age in both urban and rural settings. Our findings reveal significant insights into the prevalence of various contraceptive methods and the multifaceted factors impacting women's contraceptive decisions.

Contraceptive Use Patterns: The most commonly used contraceptive method in our study was oral contraceptive pills (OCPs), followed by condoms and intrauterine devices (IUDs). This aligns with global trends where OCPs are frequently chosen due to their high efficacy, ease of use, and additional health benefits, such as regulating menstrual cycles and reducing menstrual pain. Similar findings were reported in studies conducted in Nigeria [9] and India [10], where OCPs were also the most preferred method among women of reproductive age. The preference for condoms can be attributed to their dual protection against both pregnancy and sexually transmitted infections (STIs), which is consistent with findings from studies in South Africa and Brazil.

Factors Influencing Contraceptive Choice: Our study identified several key factors influencing contraceptive choice, including accessibility and availability of contraceptives, knowledge and awareness of different methods, perceived side effects, cultural and religious beliefs, partner influence, and healthcare provider recommendations.

Accessibility and Availability: Accessibility and availability of contraceptive methods were the most significant factors influencing choice, reported by 70% of participants. This is consistent with findings from other studies that highlight the importance of ensuring a consistent supply and easy access to contraceptive services to improve uptake. For instance, a study in Kenya found that enhanced accessibility was directly correlated with increased contraceptive use among women. [11]

Knowledge and Awareness: Knowledge and awareness of different contraceptive methods influenced the choices of 60% of participants. Educational interventions and public health campaigns have been shown to increase awareness and correct misconceptions about contraceptives, thereby encouraging their use. A study in Pakistan demonstrated that women with higher levels of contraceptive knowledge were significantly more likely to use modern contraceptive methods. [12]

Perceived Side Effects: Perceived side effects were a concern for 50% of women. Fear of side

effects is a common barrier to contraceptive use and can be mitigated by providing accurate information and counselling on managing potential side effects. Research in Ethiopia indicated that addressing concerns about side effects through counselling significantly improved contraceptive uptake. [13]

Cultural and Religious Beliefs: Cultural and religious beliefs influenced the contraceptive choices of 30% of participants. In many cultures, traditional beliefs and religious teachings play a significant role in shaping attitudes toward contraception. A study in Indonesia found that religious beliefs were an important predictor of contraceptive use, with more conservative beliefs associated with lower contraceptive use. [14]

Partner Influence: Partner influence was reported by 40% of women as an essential factor in their contraceptive choices. This finding is supported by studies in Ghana and Bangladesh, where male partner support and communication were crucial determinants of contraceptive use among women. [15, 16]

Healthcare Provider Recommendations: Healthcare provider recommendations influenced the choices of 45% of participants. Positive interactions with healthcare providers and their endorsement of specific contraceptive methods have been shown to impact women's choices significantly. A study in the United States highlighted that women were more likely to use contraceptives when recommended by a trusted healthcare provider. [17]

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study provides a comprehensive analysis of the patterns of contraceptive use and the factors influencing contraceptive choices among women of reproductive age. The findings reveal a predominance of oral contraceptive pills and highlight the significant impact of accessibility, knowledge, perceived side effects, cultural and religious beliefs, partner influence, and healthcare provider recommendations on contraceptive choices. These insights underscore the importance of targeted educational and accessibility-focused interventions to enhance contraceptive uptake and reproductive health outcomes, particularly in addressing the diverse needs and concerns of women in both urban and rural settings.

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